

Exploring Distributed Leadership as a Catalyst for Basic School Improvement in the Ghanaian Context

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Abstract

School leadership is considered a critical factor in educational success. This study explored the perception of distributed leadership practices as a catalyst for school improvement. This qualitative research draws on phenomenological experience of 15 headteachers and teachers from public basic schools in the Tafo-Pankrono Municipal, Ashanti Region, Ghana. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and analysed thematically. The findings revealed that distributed leadership improves instructional quality and staff collaboration, resulting in better student outcomes and school performance. The study further revealed that distributed leadership fosters ownership and engagement among staff by promoting shared responsibilities, collaboration, and active participation in school management. Additionally, the study revealed that distributed leadership reduces headteachers' workload, creating a more equitable task distribution that fosters teamwork and ensures no aspect of school management is overlooked. The study concludes that adopting distributed leadership practices can significantly enhance school performance and ensure sustainable improvement. The study recommends that headteachers share administrative tasks to allow more time to focus on instructional leadership. The study recommends headteachers need to relinquish power and authority and shift away from leadership as position to leadership as interaction. The study further recommends that headteachers need to build a high degree of reciprocal trust to negotiate successfully the fault lines of formal and informal leadership practice.

Keywords: *Distributed leadership, Decision-making, School improvement, Teachers.*

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Introduction

School leadership is regarded as one of the most critical indicators of educational success globally. Headteachers, as primary leaders in educational institutions, play an important role in creating, guiding, and ensuring that schools follow pedagogical and operational procedures (Nicholas, 2019) but one leader do not single-handedly lead schools to greatness; leadership involves an array of individuals with various tools and structures. As a result, traditional leadership, which equates school leadership chiefly with an individual leader, typically the headteacher, consisting of a single leader in charge of all leadership activities, has been replaced with more dynamic and flexible models, such as the distributed leadership model (Ibrahim et al., 2018; Rashid, 2022). The distributed leadership model encourages shared decisions and the allocation of leadership roles among educators, enabling collaborative problem solving and communal ownership.

Leadership paradigms in education have undergone significant evolution, particularly in the context of social justice and organizational management. The scientific exploration of leadership structures, especially concerning distributed leadership (DL) within educational settings, has gained notable traction in recent scholarly discourse (Karakose et al., 2023). A

The distributed leadership approach involves shared decision-making and responsibilities among staff, allowing for collaborative problem solving and collective ownership of school objectives (Chitpin, 2020). The idea of the distributed leadership approach is that leadership should not be about one person, but rather dispersed across a team, drawing on the strengths, expertise, and perspectives of all members. This approach allows the headteachers and teachers to take on responsibility, with collaborative decision making, and tackling the many multi-dimensional challenges of today's education (Or Berkovich, 2023). Such collaboration definitely does not just boost school management efficiency but also increase job satisfaction of the teachers because they sense that they are more empowered to play a very meaningful role in school development. This claim is in line with Harris and Elliott (2020) assertion that successful organisations including schools that practice distributed leadership model, are characterized with teamwork, collaboration, and collective problem-solving. However, while distributed leadership has attracted attention in multiple regions and contexts, there still remains the challenge of applying it. In countries where education system is centralized, like Malaysia, this leadership approach encounters its own challenges as a consequence of cultural and structural norms (Hallinger, 2004). The complexities of integrating distributed leadership within a centralized context are well illustrated in Malaysia's national education blueprint and hence calls for targeted strategies to bridge cultural divides and empower leaders in every school level (Ministry of Education, 2013). In an era where more and more nations are citing international standards, like Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) as yardsticks to measure performance for its reforms, distributed leadership becomes an instrument for ensuring international competitiveness and school excellence. Research clearly shows that distributed leadership leads to organizational commitment of teachers, a collaborative spirit and enhances overall school performance (Williams & Young,

2022). Despite its advantages, distributed leadership also comes with some challenges including a culture of trust, effective communication, and the willingness of school leaders to relinquish sole authority (Dampson et al., 2019). This means that distributed leadership must be based on a system of support for leadership including professional development, to cultivate leadership capabilities at all levels and to coordinate members towards a shared concept of school improvement.

Statement of the Problem

Effective school leadership is critical for fostering a positive educational environment and achieving improved student outcomes. In Ghana, while the concept of distributed leadership has gained traction, its practical implementation remains fraught with challenges. Many headteachers exhibit reluctance to delegate leadership responsibilities to teachers, often stemming from concerns about power dynamics, fears of losing control, and apprehension about the potential inefficiencies that may arise from shared decision-making. This reluctance not only hampers the effectiveness of distributed leadership but also stifles collaboration and innovation within schools.

Current literature in Ghana emphasizes that distributed leadership is linked to increased teacher commitment and empowerment; however, there is a notable lack of research focusing on the perceptions of both headteachers and teachers regarding its implementation and its effects on school improvement. Studies by Dampson et al. (2019), Ibrahim (2022), and Nurudeen & Alhassan (2022) primarily examine outcomes such as academic performance, teacher empowerment, and commitment. Despite the growing interest in distributed leadership, limited attention has been paid to exploring the perceptions that influence its practice within the Ghanaian context. The interplay between distributed leadership and school improvement, particularly from the perspectives of headteachers and teachers, remains significantly under-researched. This study seeks to bridge these gaps by examining the perceptions of Ghanaian headteachers and teachers on distributed leadership practices and its effects on school improvement. This research explores the perception of distributed leadership practices and its effects on school improvement, aiming to generate meaningful insights to inform leadership practices and develop more effective educational strategies tailored to the unique challenges of Ghanaian schools.

Literature Review

Historical Context of Distributed Leadership

The concept of distributed leadership has its roots in early theories of leadership and organizational behaviour, with some foundational ideas tracing back to the work of Gibbs in 1954 (Gronn & Hamilton, 2004). However, the notion of distributing leadership responsibilities is not entirely new; its precursors can be identified as far back as the mid-1920s. Over the decades, the discourse around leadership has evolved significantly. Earlier models primarily emphasized the role of a single leader possessing formal authority, reflecting a more hierarchical view of organizational dynamics. As educational institutions faced increasingly complex challenges, the need for collaborative leadership approaches became evident. This paradigm shift provided the foundation for a more inclusive and participatory understanding of leadership, paving the way for the development of the distributed leadership model (Spillane et al., 2012).

The modern understanding of distributed leadership, particularly in educational settings, emerged prominently in the late 1990s and early 2000s, marking a significant

transformation in how leadership is perceived and enacted within schools (Harris & Spillane, 2013). Scholars such as Spillane and Gronn have been pivotal in shaping the discourse around distributed leadership in education (Lumby, 2013). They argue that traditional views of leadership fail to encapsulate the dynamic nature of educational leadership, which operates across multiple levels of an organization and involves various participants. This contemporary perspective emphasizes the importance of collaboration, shared responsibility, and collective engagement in fostering school improvement and enhancing student outcomes. By recognizing the contributions of various stakeholders, the distributed leadership model advocates for a more holistic approach to leadership that reflects the realities of modern educational environments.

Contextualizing Distributed Leadership

Despite the extensive literature on distributed leadership, achieving a consensus on its definition remains a challenge for researchers and practitioners. The literature is diverse and broad-based, encompassing various interpretations and applications of the concept (Bennett et al., 2003; Harris, 2010). Botha (2014) emphasizes the complexity of the leadership concept, noting that definitions of distributed leadership often depend on the viewpoint of the individual defining it and the specific context in which it is applied. According to Leithwood et al. (2009), distributed leadership involves the regular division of responsibilities among organizational members to mitigate the risks associated with sole leadership models. This perspective highlights the idea that shared leadership can lead to more informed decision-making, as multiple individuals contribute their knowledge and expertise. Spillane et al. (2012) further challenge the traditional view of leadership by asserting that leadership responsibilities should not rest solely with individuals in formal positions of authority. Instead, they advocate for a model of leadership that spans multiple levels of the organization, facilitating improvement and innovation.

Distributed leadership shares commonalities with several related leadership frameworks, including collaborative leadership, shared leadership, and participative leadership. Collaborative leadership emphasizes joint decision-making and teamwork, akin to the collective decision-making processes inherent in distributed leadership (Wallace, 2002). Shared leadership, as defined by Pearce and Conger (2003), aligns closely with distributed leadership by promoting the distribution of responsibilities among various organizational members. Participative leadership, described by Vroom and Yago (1998), also resonates with the principles of distributed leadership, as it focuses on including members in decision-making processes. Despite these overlaps, it is essential to recognize that distributed leadership is often misinterpreted as synonymous with any form of shared leadership. Bush (2019) warns against the misconception that distributed leadership implies that everyone in an organization leads simultaneously. While all leadership involves some degree of distribution, true distributed leadership requires careful consideration of roles, responsibilities, and the contexts in which leadership is exercised.

Distributed Leadership Approach in Schools

Distributed leadership has emerged as a significant paradigm in educational leadership, reflecting a shift from traditional, hierarchical leadership models to more collaborative approaches that recognize the contributions of various stakeholders in the school community. This concept is rooted in the understanding that effective leadership is not solely the responsibility of one individual, typically the headteacher or principal, but is a collective endeavour that engages teachers and other staff members in

decision-making processes. As schools face increasingly complex challenges, distributed leadership is viewed as a promising strategy to enhance organizational effectiveness and improve student outcomes (Spillane, 2006). One of the foundational theories underpinning distributed leadership is the idea of leadership as a shared social practice. Spillane et al. (2001) argue that leadership should be viewed through the lens of social interactions among individuals within the school context. This perspective emphasizes the importance of collaboration and communication among teachers, headteachers, and support staff in fostering a shared vision for school improvement. By distributing leadership roles, schools can leverage the diverse skills and expertise of their staff, ultimately leading to more informed decision-making and a greater sense of ownership among all stakeholders (Harris, 2008).

In Ghana, studies have begun to explore the perceptions of headteachers and teachers regarding distributed leadership in schools. For instance, Ibrahim (2022) examined the impact of distributed leadership on teacher empowerment and academic performance, finding that teachers who participated in leadership roles reported higher levels of job satisfaction and commitment. However, there remains a gap in understanding how headteachers and teachers perceive the interplay between distributed leadership and school improvement. Nurudeen and Alhassan (2022) also emphasize the need for further research into the nuanced perceptions that influence the practice of distributed leadership within Ghanaian schools. The current literature suggests that while distributed leadership has been recognized as a valuable approach to enhancing school performance, the need for a deeper understanding of its dynamics remains critical. Researchers must continue to investigate how the perceptions of both headteachers and teachers shape the implementation of distributed leadership and its effects on school improvement. Furthermore, identifying and addressing the barriers to effective distributed leadership can offer meaningful perceptions for shaping educational policies and practices in Ghana and beyond.

Effects of Distributed Leadership on School Improvement

Distributed leadership has gained recognition as a vital component of effective school management, with numerous studies highlighting its positive effects on school improvement across various global contexts. Numerous studies have explored the impacts/effects of distributed leadership on school effectiveness. Jambo and Hongde (2020) in their study found that schools with a robust distributed leadership framework demonstrated higher levels of student achievement and a more positive school culture. Similarly, Leithwood and Mascall (2008) conducted a systematic review of research on distributed leadership, concluding that the approach is linked to increased teacher collaboration, enhanced job satisfaction, and improved student outcomes. These findings suggest that distributed leadership can create an environment conducive to both professional growth for teachers and academic success for students. Research conducted in Europe (particularly the UK), North America (USA and Canada), Australia, and Africa (notably South Africa and Ghana) has consistently identified distributed leadership as a critical factor in enhancing educational outcomes (Bush, 2019; Connolly, James, & Fertig, 2019; Dampson, Mensah, & Laryea, 2019; Williams & Young, 2022).

Akin, Botha, and Triegaardt (2016) assert that the distributed leadership approach significantly contributes to improvements in teaching and learning by fostering an environment where responsibilities are shared among staff. This collaborative framework not only enhances accountability but also encourages a culture of collective efficacy among educators. Specifically, Dampson et al. (2019) found that in Ghanaian

secondary schools, the practice of distributed leadership was associated with improved student achievement, heightened teacher motivation, and a more positive school culture. Their findings suggest that the collaborative dynamics fostered by distributed leadership empower teachers, enabling them to contribute meaningfully to the school's vision and goals. However, the successful implementation of distributed leadership is not without its challenges. Harris (2010) identifies several obstacles, including entrenched administrative structures and political dynamics that may resist the redistribution of power and authority. The successful adoption of distributed leadership necessitates a cultural shift within schools, encouraging openness to sharing leadership roles and responsibilities. Brinia, Mastora, and Psoni (2020) highlight that some headteachers may isolate themselves from their teaching staff, assuming primary leadership responsibilities. This narrow perspective limits the potential contributions of teachers as leaders, undermining the collaborative ethos that distributed leadership seeks to establish. Addressing these challenges is significant for harnessing the full benefits of distributed leadership, particularly in settings where traditional leadership models dominate.

Research Methods

This section outlines the approach used to explore the perception of distributed leadership practices and its effects on school improvement, focusing on headteachers' and teachers' experiences in basic schools.

Research Design

A phenomenological design, anchored in a qualitative approach, was employed for the investigation. According to Creswell (2017), a qualitative approach is appropriate for studies that aim to uncover a deeper understanding of a phenomenon and related experiences, which aligns with the focus of this study. The phenomenological design was adopted to explore the lived experiences and perceptions of Ghanaian headteachers and teachers regarding distributed leadership practices. The study sought to understand how head teachers and teachers were experiencing distributed leadership in their specific school, with their specific staff, but also in relation to their own understandings of leadership which were different from distributed leadership. Ultimately, the phenomenology design was chosen because the researchers were interested in the subjective meaning making of the sample sample and not the process of distributed leadership. This design is particularly suitable for capturing the subjective meanings and personal interpretations of distributed leadership, which are crucial for understanding its effects on school improvement. Furthermore, the phenomenological design was chosen for its strength in enabling researchers to delve deeply into how participants experience and conceptualize distributed leadership within their specific educational and cultural contexts, thereby ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon.

Population

The study population consists of headteachers and teachers from public basic schools within the Tafo-Pankrono Municipal in the Ashanti Region of Ghana.

Sample Size

The sample size for this study is fifteen (15) participants. Having 15 participants in a qualitative study is appropriate and reliable since data saturation in qualitative studies can be reached in an array of interviews from 9 to 17 (Hennink & Kaiser, 2022).

Akin, Yin (2018) opined that succumbing two to ten samples in qualitative research is considered sufficient to reach saturation levels. For this study, saturation was reached after the 15th informant, when the information provided began to repeat similar elements already expressed by previous informants. What matters most for qualitative rigor is credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. In order to enhance the trustworthiness of the data, we maintained a reflective journal where field notes were documented, capture inquiries, insights and correlations between codes and categories by way of memos insights. We also organized member checking which allowed the participants to validate the data.

Sampling Procedure

A combination of probability and non-probability sampling technique was employed to select participant. A total of five public basic schools were purposively chosen, from which the sample for the study was derived. These five schools were within the Tafo-Pankrono municipality. Public basic schools were selected because they primarily employ professionally trained teachers, whereas many private basic schools in Ghana often lack qualified teachers and headteachers. A census sampling technique was used to select all five headteachers from the schools to participate in the study. The inclusion of headteachers is based on their role as the primary leaders in their institutions, who play a crucial part in implementing and shaping leadership strategies. Therefore, their perceptions and experiences are essential for examining the effects of distributed leadership practices on school improvement. Including all five headteachers ensures the study captures diverse perspectives and provides a holistic view of leadership dynamics across the schools, thereby enhancing the validity and depth of the findings. Ten teachers were selected using a purposive sampling technique, specifically through a criterion sampling approach. The teachers were selected based on the criterion that they each had at least nine years of teaching experience at the school. To ensure a varied sample, two teachers from each school who met the criteria were randomly selected using simple random sampling. This multi-step selection process allowed the researchers to focus on teachers with significant experience in the school, ensuring the inclusion of informed perspectives for the study.

Research Instrument

A semi-structured interview guide was developed by the researchers to conduct face-to-face interviews with the headteachers and teachers sampled for the study. The interview aimed to investigate whether the distributed leadership approach was practiced in their schools and to explore its effects on overall school improvement. The interview guide was divided into two sections: Section A for the headteachers and Section B for the teachers. Each section contained five questions, all designed to explore participants' understanding and support of distributed leadership practices, its importance, and its perceived effects on school improvement. To ensure the validity and reliability of the instrument, the researchers sought expert reviews. Numerous revisions were made to the instrument, both in terms of content and structure, based on the feedback provided by experts. These revisions enhanced the clarity of the questions and ensured that the data collected during the interviews would be accurate. This review process significantly strengthened the quality of the instrument. Additionally, the researchers' decision to engage headteachers and teachers with at least nine years of experience in their schools further enhanced the credibility of the data collection process. This criterion ensured that participants had sufficient knowledge and experience to provide meaningful responses, thereby strengthening the credibility of the findings.

Data Analysis

The data collected from the interviews was analysed qualitatively using a systematic approach. A bottom-up, inductive method of thematic analysis was employed to explore and interpret the data. Initially, the recorded responses from participants were transcribed verbatim, providing the researchers with an opportunity to immerse themselves in the data and become familiar with its content. Following the transcription, the researchers began the coding process. Codes were generated to identify key concepts, phrases, and patterns within the data. This process involved breaking down the data into manageable segments and categorizing similar responses to identify emerging themes. These codes were refined through an iterative process of reviewing and comparing, ensuring that they were meaningful and representative of the data. The identified codes were then grouped into broader themes, which were carefully scrutinized and validated to ensure they accurately reflected the rich and nuanced experiences of the participants. Themes were developed through an ongoing process of comparison, refinement, and validation, ensuring the analysis remained grounded in the data and aligned with the research objectives. Thematic analysis was chosen because it is a flexible and widely used method in qualitative research, particularly when the research aims to explore participants' perceptions and experiences in-depth (Clarke & Braun, 2018). This approach allowed for a thorough exploration of the data, facilitating the identification of patterns and insights that were central to understanding the perceived effects of distributed leadership practices in Ghanaian schools.

Results and Discussion

The study sought to explore the perceptions of headteachers and teachers regarding distributed leadership practices and its effects on school improvement. A phenomenological qualitative approach was employed, and the data collected were analysed thematically. The objective of using the phenomenological qualitative approach was to gain a comprehensive and descriptive understanding of distributed leadership practices by exploring the lived experiences and perspectives of the participants. Data were gathered through in-depth interviews, which provided valuable insights into how the distribution of leadership responsibilities within schools influences various aspects of school improvement.

A series of face-to-face interviews were conducted with participants to gain an in-depth understanding of their perceptions of distributed leadership practices and the effects these practices have on school improvement. Through careful analysis of the responses, several key themes and sub-themes were identified, as outlined in Table 1, which is now discussed in detail. These themes offer valuable insights into the participants' experiences and views, highlighting the critical aspects of distributed leadership in the context of Ghanaian schools.

Table 1 Themes and Sub-Themes Emerged from the Interview Excerpt

Thematic Category	Sub-themes
Perceived Effects of Distributed Leadership and School Improvement	Improved Efficiency and Workload Management Fostering Ownership and Engagement Among Staff Collaborative Problem-Solving and Responsiveness Empowered Decision-Making and Innovation

Improved Efficiency and Workload Management

Under the main theme "Perceived Effects of Distributed Leadership Practices and School Improvement," Improved Efficiency and Workload Management emerged as a sub-theme for discussion. This sub-theme highlights how distributed leadership practices, such as the delegation and sharing of leadership roles among school staff, contribute to effective school operations. Participants shared their views on how the distribution of leadership roles reduces individual workloads, fosters teamwork, and promotes shared responsibility. These practices were perceived to enhance school improvement by enabling teachers and headteachers to focus on specific roles, thereby increasing productivity, encouraging collaboration, and improving the overall functioning of the school. These perspectives are reflected in the following interview excerpts:

When leadership roles are shared among the staff, it makes our work much easier. Assuming I am in charge of academics, I can concentrate on improving lesson plans and monitoring student progress without worrying about unrelated tasks. Distributed leadership also creates a collaborative environment because everyone knows they have a part to play in achieving the school's goals. Distributed leadership, in my experience, really helps to improve academic performance because we can focus better and work more efficiently (Teacher 1).

If one person handles two or more responsibilities, the person may not have the time to manage everything properly. Sharing leadership roles lightens the workload for everyone and brings unity among the staff. Let us say, I am given a role that aligns with my skills, I can perform better and make a bigger impact. It is not just about reducing stress for the headteacher; it is about ensuring that every part of the school runs smoothly because the responsibilities are evenly distributed (Teacher 2).

When responsibilities are distributed, the headteacher does not carry the entire burden alone. Instead, it is shared among all of us, and that means we all work harder to achieve our common goals. I have seen how this approach boosts teamwork and productivity in the school. Everyone contributes their strengths, and the school becomes more efficient because we are all working together to move forward (Teacher 3).

Teamwork makes a big difference in how the school performs. If we all work together, it is easier to achieve our goals. But if some people are working hard while others are sitting back, it creates problems. Distributed leadership ensures that everyone has a role to play, and that balance is important for the school to function well. It also motivates us because we feel like we are all part of the process (Teacher 10).

In the past, it was just me and my assistant headteacher taking on everything, and it was overwhelming. Now that we have started sharing responsibilities, I feel more at ease. I can now step into class and teach without constantly being called away to attend to parents or deal with administrative tasks. This approach has really helped the school operate more smoothly (Headteacher 1).

From the interviews, it is evident that teachers and headteachers perceive distributed leadership practices as vital to fostering school improvement. These practices influence key areas such as workload management, teamwork, and operational efficiency. For instance, Teacher 1 highlighted how distributed leadership allows teachers to prioritize core academic responsibilities, such as lesson planning and student monitoring, rather than being burdened by unrelated administrative tasks. This focus on academic duties enhances instructional quality and student outcomes, aligning with Botha and Triegaardt (2016) assertion that distributed leadership enhances instructional capacity through the effective utilization of individuals' expertise.

Teacher 2 emphasized the importance of aligning leadership roles with individual skills. When roles are distributed according to staff members' competencies, their strengths are maximized, leading to improved performance and streamlined school operations. This observation is consistent with Leithwood et al.'s (2009) findings that effective role alignment contributes to organizational efficiency and school improvement. Moreover, sharing responsibilities reduces the headteacher's workload, creating a more equitable task distribution that fosters teamwork and ensures no aspect of school management is overlooked.

Teacher 3 discussed the collective benefits of distributed leadership in promoting teamwork and productivity. Shared leadership responsibilities encourage staff members to work collaboratively toward common goals, enhancing unity and operational efficiency. This reflects Gronn and Hamilton (2004) "concertive action" concept, which posits that distributed leadership generates synergy among team members, ultimately driving organizational success.

Similarly, Teacher 10 accentuated the value of equitable task distribution in maintaining staff motivation and accountability. When responsibilities are fairly allocated, disparities in workload are minimized, motivating staff to actively contribute to school improvement. This perspective aligns with Bush and Glover's (2014) view that distributed leadership fosters a sense of ownership and commitment among team members.

Finally, a headteacher shared that adopting distributed leadership has significantly reduced their administrative burden, enabling them to concentrate on instructional leadership, such as classroom teaching. Delegating managerial responsibilities allows headteachers to concentrate on guiding educational practices, particularly in instructional leadership, as supported by Hallinger and Heck (2010).

Fostering Ownership and Engagement Among Staff

This subtheme emerged as a significant area of discussion, emphasizing the importance of encouraging active participation and a sense of responsibility among stakeholders. This sub-theme highlights the critical role of ownership and engagement in driving successful outcomes. Findings from the study revealed that participants associated fostering ownership with creating opportunities for collaboration, shared decision-making, and empowering individuals to take responsibility for specific tasks. Engagement was further linked to clear communication, motivation, and active involvement in processes, which were seen as vital for achieving shared goals. These insights can be inferred from the following interview extracts:

Distributed leadership practices are not just about giving out roles; but it is also about making people feel like they belong. When the headteacher delegates responsibilities, it encourages collaboration and a sense of togetherness. For instance, if someone is put in charge of extracurricular activities, they will feel motivated to do their best, knowing that the work is valued. On the other hand, when one person holds all the power, it can lead to division and resentment. Sharing responsibilities is better for everyone it keeps the school united and moving in the right direction (Teacher 4).

When leadership roles are distributed across the staff, it creates a sense of ownership in the school's development. We all contribute to its growth, and that collective effort accelerates improvement. Assuming that I took charge of the school's literacy programme, I collaborated with colleagues to refine our teaching methods, and the results were immediate that is students' reading scores went up. This shows that distributed leadership directly influences school improvement through the involvement of everyone in the process (Teacher 6).

Distributed leadership has been a game-changer for our school's improvement. When I delegate responsibilities, it empowers teachers to take ownership of their roles, which makes them more invested in the school's success. I assigned a team to focus on student discipline and another on extracurricular activities and it has helped us create a more balanced and engaging learning environment. This approach has not only reduced my workload but has also fostered greater accountability, resulting in a positive impact on both academic outcomes and school culture (Headteacher 5).

The quotations from participants reveals that distributed leadership fosters ownership and engagement among staff by promoting shared responsibilities, collaboration, and active participation in school management. It transcends mere delegation of tasks, focusing instead on creating an inclusive environment where individuals feel valued and integral to the school's progress. Teacher 4 noted that distributing responsibilities enhances unity and motivation. For instance, assigning a staff member to oversee extracurricular activities not only motivates them to excel but also strengthens their sense of belonging. Conversely, centralizing leadership can breed division and resentment. This aligns with Giubertoni (2024) argument that distributed leadership enhances staff cohesion by ensuring individuals feel connected to the organization's mission and goals. The teacher further highlighted how distributed leadership fosters a participatory culture where decisions are collectively made, which minimizes hierarchical barriers and increases trust among staff. This resonates with Noman's (2023) emphasis on the importance of trust and collaboration in enhancing organizational effectiveness. When staff members are actively involved in decision-making processes, they feel a stronger commitment to the school's vision and goals, which significantly affects their willingness to go above and beyond in their roles.

Similarly, Teacher 6 opined that distributed leadership enables staff to take proactive measures to address challenges, which leads to immediate and effective solutions. This adaptive capacity, nurtured through shared leadership, aligns with Dampson et al.'s (2019) assertion that empowering employees encourages innovative thinking and builds resilience within organizations. For instance, delegating the literacy programme responsibilities not only improved reading outcomes but also strengthened teachers' confidence in their capabilities to drive improvement initiatives.

Additionally, Headteacher 5's reflection on creating specialized teams for student discipline and extracurricular activities illustrates how distributed leadership facilitates a targeted approach to problem-solving. This approach is supported by Ho et al. (2016), who found that distributing leadership responsibilities allows school leaders to concentrate on high-impact areas such as instructional quality, while staff members manage operational tasks. Such division of labour not only increases efficiency but also ensures that all aspects of school management receive adequate attention.

Distributed leadership also cultivates a sense of shared accountability. Teacher 6 pointed out that involving staff in leadership roles ensures that everyone feels responsible for the school's success, which mitigates the risk of complacency. Holloway and Holloway (2021) emphasize that leadership is most effective when it is dispersed across multiple actors, creating an environment where accountability is collective rather than individualized. This shared accountability reinforces a culture of high expectations and continuous improvement, which directly influence school performance.

Moreover, fostering ownership through distributed leadership supports long-term school improvement by nurturing future leaders within the organization. As staff

members are given opportunities to lead, they develop essential skills and confidence that prepare them for more significant leadership roles. Harris and Jones (2020) highlight that distributed leadership not only improves immediate outcomes but also builds leadership capacity, ensuring the sustainability of progress over time.

Collaborative Problem-Solving and Responsiveness

This subtheme, as identified from interviews with teachers and headteachers, highlights the significant effect of distributed leadership practices on school improvement, particularly through fostering collaborative problem-solving and responsiveness. The findings reveal that distributing leadership roles enables schools to address challenges more efficiently and utilize the diverse expertise of their staff. This approach promotes teamwork, enhances decision-making processes, and leads to innovative solutions that improve student engagement, discipline, and professional development. Such collaborative efforts not only strengthen the operational effectiveness of schools but also contribute to sustained improvements in overall performance. These insights can be deduced from the transcribed interviews as follows.

For me, distribution of leadership roles in schools makes the schools become more responsive to challenges. With this approach each teacher brings their expertise to the table, which leads to faster solutions. For instance, when we decided on engaging students in extracurricular activities, the teachers responsible for it introduced new programmes for us to engage them. This collaboration helped improve student morale and overall school performance (Teacher 5).

In my view, when leadership is shared, we see better results, especially with teamwork. A typical example is, if teachers work together on discipline issues, we are able to enforce rules more effectively than if one person is trying to handle everything. It is also about bringing diverse ideas together. Distributed leadership helps us tap into everyone's expertise, and that makes the school operation effective and in turn improve on the school performance (Headteacher 2).

One of the greatest benefits of distributed leadership is how it fosters a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement. Teachers, when given leadership roles, are more motivated to enhance their areas. I remember some time ago I was tasked with overseeing teacher professional development, and I implemented more regular training sessions. This led to noticeable improvements in teaching quality, as well as a more effective student engagement (Teacher 8).

Distributing leadership is a key driver of school improvement because it allows us to tap into each teacher's strengths. When responsibilities are shared, everyone feels empowered to contribute ideas and solutions. Let us say we have come together to work towards developing a new student support programme, our diverse skills we bring to this project would be highly effective and would lead to improving students' performance (Headteacher 3).

The interview voices highlight the role of distributed leadership practices in fostering collaborative problem-solving and responsiveness, which are critical drivers of school improvement. Distributed leadership enables schools to harness the collective expertise of their staff, fostering a sense of shared responsibility and encouraging innovation in addressing challenges (Brinia, Mastora, & Psoni, 2020). Promoting teamwork and empowering teachers to take leadership roles in specific areas enables schools to implement more effective solutions to issues such as student engagement, discipline, and professional development. Research by Harris and Jones (2020) supports these findings, emphasizing that distributed leadership enhances decision-making processes by involving diverse perspectives, ultimately leading to improved school performance. Similarly, Leithwood (2021) argue that empowering teachers through leadership roles not only builds their capacity but also motivates them to take

ownership of school improvement initiatives. For instance, collaborative efforts to introduce new student support programmes or improve discipline practices often result in greater stakeholder engagement and higher levels of satisfaction among both teachers and students.

Moreover, evidence suggests that schools practicing distributed leadership are better positioned to adapt to dynamic educational demands. Bush (2019) notes that fostering a culture of collaboration encourages continuous professional development among teachers, enhancing their skills and boosting overall teaching quality. This aligns with the findings of this study, where participants described distributed leadership as a means to implement innovative training programmes that positively impacted both teaching and student learning outcomes.

Empowered Decision-Making and Innovation

The subtheme "Empowered Decision-Making and Innovation" also emerged under the main theme of the effect of distributed leadership practices on school improvement. This subtheme reflects how the distribution of leadership responsibilities has empowered teachers and school leaders to make informed decisions, foster innovation, and address specific challenges. This collaborative approach has led to improved school performance and enhanced educational outcomes. The following excerpts illustrate these points:

Distributed leadership has significantly improved the school's academic performance. Sharing responsibilities enables us to focus on specific areas, such as student progress and curriculum development. When tasked with monitoring student performance, I implemented targeted interventions that enhanced student achievement. This collective approach drives school improvement effectively (Teacher 5).

Shared leadership prevents any one individual from being overburdened, allowing for a more focused and efficient approach to school improvement. With leadership roles distributed, we can dedicate time and effort to our specific responsibilities. Coordinating the school's assessment practices enabled me to develop effective strategies for evaluating student progress, leading to better learning outcomes (Teacher 9).

Embracing distributed leadership has brought about a significant transformation in our school. Sharing leadership roles allows me to concentrate on long-term planning while teachers take on critical responsibilities that directly impact student performance. Delegating student support initiatives to a senior teacher resulted in tailored programmes to address individual needs and fostered stronger relationships between teachers and students, contributing to noticeable improvements in both student achievement and teacher collaboration (Headteacher 4).

The findings from this study provide compelling evidence of the role that distributed leadership plays in empowering decision-making and fostering innovation, which in turn significantly contributes to school improvement. As illustrated in the excerpts from teachers and headteachers, distributing leadership responsibilities allows for greater involvement of all staff members, facilitating more effective problem-solving, the implementation of targeted interventions, and continuous school-wide innovation.

Teacher 5 highlighted how the distribution of leadership roles enabled a more focused approach to key areas like student performance and curriculum development. This empowerment, particularly in monitoring student progress and implementing targeted interventions, has been shown to directly improve student achievement. According to Leithwood (2021), schools with distributed leadership benefit from teachers taking ownership of key areas, driving improvements in academic outcomes. When leadership

is shared, teachers can implement interventions more effectively, as they possess specialized knowledge and are better positioned to identify specific needs. Similarly, Nurudeen and Alhassan (2022) argue that when teachers are entrusted with leadership responsibilities, they develop innovative practices that have a direct effect on student learning and overall school performance. Therefore, the findings suggest that shared leadership facilitates a more dynamic, responsive approach to addressing educational challenges, which aligns with Harris and Jones (2020) who contend that such practices lead to continuous school improvement by tapping into the collective expertise of the staff.

Teacher 9 described how shared leadership alleviates the burden on individual teachers, leading to a more efficient and focused approach to school improvement. Delegating specific leadership tasks, such as coordinating assessment practices, enabled more effective evaluation of student progress, which ultimately contributed to improved learning outcomes. This finding supports Al-Hassanieh (2020) who argue that distributed leadership reduces individual workload and enhances task-specific focus. Teachers who are entrusted with leadership roles are empowered to take ownership of key responsibilities, which improves the quality of those processes and the outcomes associated with them. Moreover, Harris et al. (2022) points out that when leadership is shared, teachers have more time and energy to dedicate to their responsibilities, making the school more responsive to challenges and capable of improving its processes in ways that benefit students.

Further supporting the argument, Headteacher 4 emphasized how delegating leadership roles to senior teachers allowed them to take charge of student support initiatives, tailoring programmes to individual student needs. This responsibility-sharing not only strengthened relationships between teachers and students but also led to improvements in both student achievement and teacher collaboration. The transformation described in the excerpt aligns with Youngs et al. (2021), who note that distributed leadership enhances collaboration among teachers, leading to innovative practices that directly affect student engagement and academic performance. Modeste et al. (2022) highlights that when teachers assume leadership roles, they feel a stronger sense of ownership and accountability, which positively influences their commitment to school improvement. In this case, the delegation of leadership responsibilities led to the creation of personalized learning programmes that directly addressed student needs, contributing to better student outcomes and overall school performance.

Distributed leadership, as seen in the participants' experiences, contributes to school improvement by fostering a culture of empowered decision-making and innovation. Or Berkovich (2023) asserts that the collaborative nature of distributed leadership encourages school leaders and teachers to work together to solve problems and develop innovative solutions. This collaborative decision-making ensures that decisions are informed by diverse perspectives, leading to more effective and sustainable solutions. Additionally, Harris and Elliot (2020) argue that distributed leadership creates an environment where continuous improvement is possible, as it encourages experimentation and the development of new strategies that respond to the evolving needs of students.

Summary of Findings

1. The study found that distributed leadership significantly enhances workload management, allowing teachers to focus on core academic responsibilities such as lesson planning and student monitoring. This reduction in administrative burden

enables teachers to improve the quality of their instruction, which directly affects student outcomes. As teachers concentrate on academic duties, the effectiveness of their teaching increases, leading to improved overall school performance.

2. The study further revealed that aligning leadership roles with staff members' competencies enhances operational efficiency. When leadership tasks are distributed based on individual strengths, staff can perform more effectively in their respective areas. This improves the functioning of the school and ensures better resource management, contributing to smoother school operations. Also, the distribution of tasks alleviates the headteacher's workload, which promotes collaboration and fosters a more cohesive school environment, ultimately strengthening the school's capacity for improvement.

3. Additionally, shared leadership responsibilities were found to promote greater collaboration and synergy among teachers. When working together toward common goals, staff members create a more unified approach, enhancing operational efficiency. This collective effort fosters a positive school culture where all members feel responsible for the success of the institution, contributing to continuous school improvement.

4. Equitable task distribution was also found to motivate staff and increase accountability. When responsibilities are fairly allocated, staff feel more valued and take greater ownership of their roles. This heightened sense of ownership encourages staff to contribute more actively to school improvement, fostering a culture of high expectations and continuous growth. Increased motivation and accountability lead to better outcomes in both student performance and school operations.

5. Furthermore, the study found that distributed leadership reduces the administrative burden on headteachers, enabling them to focus more on instructional leadership. This shift in focus allows headteachers to provide better guidance and support to teachers, which is essential for improving the quality of education. As headteachers concentrate on instructional leadership, student outcomes improve, and overall school performance is enhanced.

6. The study also revealed that distributed leadership fosters a sense of ownership and motivation among staff, making them feel integral to the school's progress. This increased sense of belonging and commitment leads to higher levels of engagement, collaboration, and innovation. Teachers who feel valued are more likely to actively participate in school improvement initiatives, which has a direct positive impact on the school's performance.

7. Moreover, the study found that distributed leadership promotes collaboration and trust among staff. A participatory culture helps break down hierarchical barriers, encouraging collective decision-making. This culture of collaboration strengthens staff cohesion and ensures that the school is aligned with its shared goals, leading to more efficient decision-making and improved school outcomes.

8. Delegating leadership roles in specific areas, such as student discipline or extracurricular activities, was found to lead to more focused problem-solving. This approach ensures that key areas of the school are well-managed, enhancing operational efficiency. As a result, school operations become more streamlined, contributing to the overall improvement of the school environment.

9. The study further found that shared accountability, which is central to distributed leadership, motivates staff to engage more actively in school improvement

efforts. Involving staff in leadership roles encourages them to take ownership of the school's success. This shared accountability helps maintain a high standard of performance and supports the continuous improvement of the school.

10. Finally, the study revealed that distributed leadership helps build leadership capacity within the school. Providing opportunities for staff to develop leadership skills ensures that the school nurtures future leaders, creating sustainability for long-term school improvement. The development of leadership capacity within the school contributes to continuous progress and improvement over time.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concludes that distributed leadership significantly contributes to school improvement through the promotion of a more collaborative, efficient, and empowered school environment. The delegation of leadership roles allows teachers to concentrate on core academic responsibilities, which improves instructional quality and enhances student outcomes. Additionally, aligning leadership responsibilities with teachers' skills and competencies enhances operational efficiency and promotes teamwork, leading to improved school performance.

The study further concludes that sharing leadership roles fosters a sense of ownership and accountability among staff, motivating them to contribute more effectively to school improvement initiatives. Reducing the administrative burden on headteachers enables them to focus on instructional leadership, resulting in a direct positive impact on the quality of education provided.

Moreover, distributed leadership enhances problem-solving capabilities, empowering staff to proactively address challenges and develop innovative solutions. The collective involvement of staff in decision-making processes and the establishment of specialized teams for targeted areas, such as student discipline and extracurricular activities, ensures that all aspects of school management are managed effectively.

Recommendations

The study recommends that headteachers delegate leadership responsibilities across various levels of staff to allow teachers to focus on core academic duties such as lesson planning and student monitoring. This delegation will enable teachers to enhance instructional quality, which directly impacts student outcomes and overall school performance. Additionally, leadership roles should be aligned with staff skills and competencies, ensuring that tasks are assigned according to individual strengths. This approach will maximize efficiency, improve performance, and create a more streamlined operational environment.

The study further recommends that schools foster a culture of collaboration and teamwork among staff. Encouraging shared leadership responsibilities will help build trust, unity, and operational efficiency, benefiting the school as a whole. To ensure a sense of collective responsibility, schools should involve staff members in leadership roles, motivating them to actively contribute to school improvement efforts and reducing the burden on individual leaders.

Moreover, it is recommended that headteachers focus more on instructional leadership and distribute administrative tasks among other staff to reduce their administrative

workload. Distributing administrative tasks among other staff members will free up time for headteachers to concentrate on guiding educational practices, thereby improving teaching quality.

The study also suggests empowering teachers to take part in decision-making processes. Involving staff in strategic decisions will promote innovation and increase their sense of ownership over school goals and initiatives. Schools should also consider forming specialized teams to handle specific tasks such as student discipline, extracurricular activities, and professional development. This approach will ensure that all aspects of school management receive sufficient attention and will improve overall operational efficiency.

Finally, the study recommends investing in professional development opportunities to build leadership capacity among teachers. Preparing teachers for future leadership roles will ensure the sustainability of distributed leadership practices and contribute to long-term school improvement.

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